

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF THE LAUREL PLANT

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Abstract: This article provides necessary recommendations on the medicinal properties, morphology and cultivation technology of the medicinal ginger plant.

Key words: laurel, agrotechnics, essential oil, dried leaves of the laurel tree, refreshing. Bay leaf has a weak smell and a bitter taste. It is widely used in cooking and canning. First meals - soups (with meat, vegetables, fish and others). Gives a great taste to second dishes (mutton and beef, boiled and steamed fish dishes). It is also combined with vegetable dishes with beans, chickpeas, legumes. Compared to other spices, bay leaves can be added to first dishes 5 minutes before cooking, and to second dishes 7-10 minutes before cooking. 1-2 to 3-4 leaves are added to the dish. Bay leaves are removed from the finished dish. In Western Europe, bay leaves are added to some jams and some desserts.

Dried laurel leaf, aromatic spice. Contains up to 3% essential oil. The bay leaf used in cooking is dark green, light green in color, short-ribbed, and tastier. When added to liquid and thick foods, soups (5 minutes before cooking for liquid foods, 10 minutes before cooking for thick foods), it gives a unique taste and aroma, it is added to pickles; It is used in goose, duck, fish, canning and confectionery industries. For pickling, 3-4 leaves are used for 100 kg of cabbage. (from "UzME")

Laurel leaves in the form of tincture or decoction have been used in traditional folk medicine for the treatment of various diseases in all regions of the world - in Eastern and Western Europe, as well as in Asia.

Bay leaves are sold in markets and shops. It is a powerful natural antibiotic and a catalyst of metabolic processes.

Benefits of bay leaf decoction

The decoction accelerates the excretion of various harmful salts accumulated in the body. The active substances in this decoction help to remove the stones that have appeared in the gall bladder, salts collected in the joints, and also help to get rid of colds characteristic of cholecystitis.

The decoction is very useful for diabetes and hemorrhoids (in this case, it is necessary to consult a treating doctor).

These recommendations are not for consuming this decoction every day for a long time, because the course of treatment for consuming it cannot be increased for more than three weeks in a year.

Laurel tincture

Tincture from the decoction has a milder effect on the body, it is often consumed in case of diarrhea.

In addition, if a little honey is added to this tincture, it becomes an effective remedy against colds.

It is also interesting that this drug is unique against diabetes and reduces the total sugar level. According to the first option, the best and most useful way to get rid of flatulence is to take a bath (one liter of this tincture is enough), and you can wipe with this tincture. Taking a bath lasts up to 15 minutes, this procedure is continued for a week.

According to the second option, bay tincture is drunk, which is a traditional way to get rid of the disease and its first symptoms with the appearance of the first signs of allergy (if necessary, drink it for several days).

The leaf of this plant is used as a spice in daily dishes, which is widely used all over the world, and is also a healing agent. We will dwell on its healing properties. Doctors have studied its healing properties for centuries. As a result, they came to the following conclusion, laurel has the following properties:

- Fights against microbes;
- Strengthens the immune system;
- Excellent anti-inflammatory agent;
- Treats injuries;
- Binder;
- Urine driver;
- Calming;
- Improves digestion.

This spice will help you solve various health problems at home.

1. It is useful to chew a bay leaf twice a day to get rid of bad breath, gingivitis or stomatitis caused by a cold, but after chewing it, refrain from eating and drinking for an hour. it is necessary to refrain.

2. Bay leaves can be used to disinfect rooms without hesitation. Take the amount of bay leaves you want, put it in a bowl, pour boiling water over it, and after 15 minutes, put the bowl in the room to be disinfected. After an hour, you will see how the room is filled with a pleasant smell and the air in it is cleaned of bacteria.

3. If you need a natural medicine against bacteria and colds, strengthening immunity or lowering blood sugar, you can use the following simple recipe. Take ten bay leaves, pour three cups of boiling water over them, then let this mixture rest for 3 hours. Drink half a glass of it 3 times a day.

4. For the treatment of skin diseases, a decoction can be prepared from the leaves of the bay leaf for the treatment of purulent, hardened swellings, and for the treatment and recovery of the limbs of the patient who have been lying in the body for a long time and become stiff and lifeless. The recipe for this is as follows: take 1 and a half spoons of ground bay leaf in a tablespoon, pour vegetable oil on it and let it rest in a dark place (not in the refrigerator). After a week, the finished medicine can be applied to the skin. will be ready.

5. Bay leaf helps to get rid of such problems when the feet sweat often and have an unpleasant smell. For this, the following mixture is prepared: Take 30 bay leaves, boil them in a glass of water and let them rest for 30-40 minutes. The mixture is placed in a bowl, the required amount of warm water is poured over it, and the feet are bathed in it for 10 minutes.

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